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The "sunshine" vitamin is a hot topic that attracted ample attention over the past decades, specially that a considerable proportion of the worldwide population are deficient in this essential nutrient. Vitamin D was primarily acknowledged for its importance in bone formation, however; increasing evidence point to its interference with the proper function of nearly every tissue in our bodies including brain, heart, muscles, immune system and skin. Thereby its deficiency has been incriminated in a long panel of diseases including cancers, autoimmune diseases, cardiovascular and neurological disorders. Its involvement in the pathogenesis of different dermatological diseases is no exception and has been the subject of much research over the recent years. In the current review, we will throw light on this highly disputed vitamin that is creating a significant concern from a dermatological perspective. Furthermore, the consequences of its deficiency on the skin will be in focus.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Deficiency, Dermatology, Immunological

Introduction

It is somewhat ironic that vitamin D, through a historical accident, became classified as a 'vitamin', owing to the fact that vitamin is conventionally defined as 'essential item needed in the diet'. The paradox with 'vitamin D' is that diet per se is usually poor in vitamin D except for cod or other fish oils or food fortified with this vitamin (1).

Vitamin D is actually a fat-soluble prohormone steroid that has endocrine, paracrine and autocrine functions (2). The endocrine effects of vitamin D are mainly involved in serum calcium homeostasis. Vitamin D and calcium are often used in the same sentence because they work closely together, vitamin D's primary role is to control the levels of calcium found in the bloodstream by constantly allowing calcium and phosphate absorption from the intestine or taking calcium from bones. Furthermore, vitamin D is an enabling agent that, when present in optimal concentrations, has no perceptible effect on calcium absorption in its own right; however, it permits or facilitates flexible physiologic response to varying calcium need (3).

The paracrine and autocrine effects of vitamin D depend on genetic transcription, unique to the type of cell expressing nuclear vitamin D receptors. These potential effects include inhibition of cell proliferation, promotion of cell differentiation, and apoptosis which may in turn have roles in cancer, immunity, and many organ systems (4-8). The potential myriad effects of this vitamin in human health and disease have led to an

escalating interest in vitamin D inadequacy and the best methods to normalize suboptimal levels.

Sources of vitamin D

There are only 3 known sources of vitamin D; sunlight, diet, and vitamin D supplements (2, 9, 10).

Vitamin D and the skin

The skin is unique in being not only the source of vitamin D for the body but also in being capable of responding to the active metabolite of vitamin D, 1,25(OH)₂D. Both 1,25(OH)₂D and its receptor (VDR) play essential roles in the skin.

Skin differentiation and proliferation

Both calcium and 1,25(OH)₂D perform important and interacting functions in regulating the skin differentiation process. 1,25(OH)₂D increases the expression of involucrin, transglutaminase, loricrin, and filaggrin and increases keratinocyte cornified envelope formation while inhibiting proliferation (9, 10). These actions are due to, at least in part, the ability of 1,25(OH)₂D to increase intracellular calcium levels achieved by induction of the calcium receptor (11), and the phospholipase C (12) that are critical for the ability of calcium to stimulate keratinocyte differentiation (13,14). Mice lacking the VDR show defective epidermal differentiation manifesting as reduced levels of involucrin and loricrin and loss of keratohyaline granules (15, 16).

Cutaneous antimicrobial effects

1,25(OH)₂D and its receptor regulate the processing of the long chain glycosylceramides that are

critical for the skin barrier formation (17) which is crucial in defending the skin. Furthermore, they induce toll like receptor 2 (TLR2) and its coreceptor CD14, that initiate the innate immune response in skin (18). Activation of these receptors leads to the induction of CYP27B1, which in turn induces cathelicidin resulting in the killing of invasive organisms (18, 19). Mice lacking the VDR or the enzyme (CYP27B1) show decreased lipid content of the lamellar bodies leading to a defective permeability barrier, and a defective response of the innate immune system to invading infections.

Vitamin D and cutaneous innate immunity

The historical link between vitamin D and innate immune function stemmed initially from the use of cod liver oil as treatment for tuberculosis (TB). More recent work has focused on the cellular and molecular machinery that underpins the actions of vitamin D on the pathogen that causes TB, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (M. TB). In the first of these studies, carried out 25 years ago, active 1,25(OH)₂D was shown to reduce the proliferation of M. TB in macrophages with this effect being enhanced by the cytokine interferon γ (IFN γ), a known stimulator of macrophages (20). However, the major advance in our understanding of how vitamin D directs antibacterial responses in TB arose from much more recent studies aiming at defining the way by which monocytes and macrophages, key cells in directing bacterial killing, respond to an encounter with M. TB (21). These data suggested that monocytes promote localized activation of vitamin D in response to M. TB, with the resulting 1,25(OH)₂D binding to endogenous VDR. In this way, vitamin D can act to modulate gene expression in response to M. TB immune challenge – a classical intracrine mechanism (22, 23). Functional analyses showed that 25OHD-mediated induction of cathelicidin is coincident with enhanced killing of M. TB in monocytes. Naturally occurring variations in serum 25OHD have been shown to correlate with induction of monocyte cathelicidin expression (24). The conclusion from these studies was that individuals with low serum 25OHD will be less able to support monocyte induction of antibacterial activity and may therefore be at greater risk of infection. Conversely, supplementation of vitamin D-insufficient individuals *in vivo* has been shown to improve TLR-mediated induction of monocyte cathelicidin (25) and may therefore help to protect against infection.

Studies have shown that T-cell cytokines play a pivotal role in both amplifying and attenuating vitamin D-mediated cathelicidin production (26). Indeed, cytokine production by monocytes themselves may be central to the intracrine metabolism of vitamin D in this cell type (27, 28). Thus, it seems likely that the ability to mount an appropriate response to infection will be highly dependent on the availability of vitamin D, with additional tuning of this response by other components of the normal human immune response.

Vitamin D can also influence innate immune responses to pathogens via effects on antigen presentation by macrophages or dendritic cells (DCs). These cells are known to express VDR (29), and treatment

with 1,25(OH)₂D has been shown to inhibit DC maturation, suppress antigen presentation and promote a tolerogenic T-cell response (30, 31).

Conclusions

In conclusion one could clearly sense the unique relationship that entangles vitamin D to dermatology. On one hand, our skin is one source for this important vitamin and on the other hand all available data point to its important impact on the health of our skin and the involvement of its deficiency in the pathway of many dermatological diseases. Several factors are responsible for maintaining it in optimum levels; therefore sunny climates are by far not a guarantee for providing a “comfort zone” regarding the possibility of this vitamin deficiency, a concern documented by several epidemiological studies carried out in areas close to the equator (32-35). On the basis of currently available data, it is clear that supplemental vitamin D should be the preferred recommendation toward achieving its normal serum levels, thereby avoiding the deleterious effects accompanied by its deficiency. Still more research is needed to unravel its complicated ties to dermatological diseases and create clear guidelines and recommendations for its supplementation.

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